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THE USE OF THICKENED AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF POLYMERS THAT IMPROVE THE OIL DISPLACEMENT REGIME

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Abstract

Currently, the need for energy is growing rapidly, it is possible to satisfy this need only by involving hard-to-recover hydrocarbon reserves in the development, and only partially by using alternative energy sources. The development of hydrocarbon deposits is increasingly associated with the development of heavy oil deposits due to the rapid reduction of conventional light oil reserves. The growing demand for oil and gas is already being partially met by a significant volume of heavy oil. Although the use of thermal methods in many projects to improve oil recovery is successful, they are often not economical enough or impractical in formations with deep and thin layers. Therefore, polymer flooding is the preferred method of oil recovery for such formations.

The deposits of Embamunaigas JSC are mostly in the final stages of development and specialists are faced with the issue of the most complete extraction of oil reserves at the same time as preventing a significant increase in the water produced along the way.

Polymer flooding is one of the highly effective methods of physical and chemical impact on the productive reservoir. The method is well suited for oil extraction in conditions of various stages of field development with uneven permeability, different reservoir properties and structure. The main property of polymers is the thickening of water, which leads to a decrease in the ratio of oil and water viscosities in the formation and a reduction in the conditions of water breakthrough due to the difference in viscosities or heterogeneity of the formation.

Keywords: Deposit, productive formation, well, polymer flooding.

The use of polymer flooding in reservoirs with light oil began more than half a century ago, and has long been considered a suitable method for oil production with a viscosity of up to 100 MPa • s. Recently, this method has attracted the attention of specialists to the extraction of heavy oil and has become promising for extracting oil from heavy oil fields with a viscosity of several hundred to several thousand MPa • s. The achievements of the last two decades in the field of polymer production have become the basis for such widespread attention to this technology in heavy oil production. This is especially true for the fields of Western Kazakhstan, as there is currently a need for an active increase in oil production in this region.

Heavy oil and bitumen account for up to 70% of the world's proven oil reserves. High density and viscosity traditionally determine the cost of their extraction compared to lighter hydrocarbons and limit the extraction of these resources to low volumes. To date, only a small part of these resources have been developed, since heavy oil extraction methods are traditionally much more expensive than conventional oil extraction methods. Nevertheless, the discovery of new light oil fields is happening less and less, and given the stabilization of oil prices, oil companies have begun to turn to unconventional resources to meet the needs of the market. This creates the basis for heavy oil to take a significant share in the energy structure in the near future [1-2].

Figure 1.1 – Distribution of world oil reserves according to Schlumberger classification [2]

The United States Geological Survey (USGS) defines [3] heavy oil as a type of crude oil characterized by an asphalt, dense, viscous structure (similar to molasses) and the content of asphaltenes (very large molecules, including about 90 percent of sulfur and metals contained in oil). It also contains impurities of resin and heavy hydrocarbons, which must be removed before processing. Despite the fact that it may be different, the upper limit of density for heavy oil is determined by the API degree of 22° (minimum density of 921.8 kg/m³) with a viscosity of 100 MPa•s. The "API degree" developed by the American Petroleum Institute is the standard for expressing the specific gravity of oil, calculated as $(141.5 / S.G.) - 131.5$, where

S.G. is the specific gravity of oil at 60 degrees Fahrenheit (15.6°C). The lower the specific gravity, the higher the API degree will be. Definitions of the type of oil are given below:

Light oil: also called "ordinary oil", light oil has an API degree of at least 22° and a viscosity of less than 100 MPa•s.

Heavy oil: asphalt, dense (low API degree) and viscous oil, which is chemically characterized by the content of asphaltenes (very large molecules that include most of the sulfur and metals in oil).

Superheavy oil: a part of heavy oil having an API degree less than 10° (density greater than 1000 kg/m³).

Natural bitumen: also called "oil sands", bitumen has the characteristics of heavy oil, but is even more dense and viscous. Natural bitumen has a viscosity of more than 10,000 MPa•s.

Compared to heavy oil, light or "ordinary" oil can be extracted without heating or dilution. Light oil is characterized by an API degree of at least 22°, and superheavy oil has an API degree of less than 10°.

Natural bitumen, also known as oil sands, have common characteristics with heavy oil, but they are even more dense and viscous - with a viscosity of more than 10,000 MPa •s. Heavy oil, as a rule, is not extracted in its natural state through a well or by conventional extraction methods. Heating or liquefaction is usually required in order for the oil to fill the well or be transported through the pipeline.

<i>API Gravity</i>	
LIGHT OIL	45.4°
	31.1°
MEDIUM	30.2°
	22.3°
HEAVY	21.5°
	10.0°
EXTRA HEAVY	6.5°
	0.1°

Figure 1.2 Graphical representation of the density of heavy oil

There is no universal relationship between the density and viscosity of oil, although oil usually turns out to be more viscous with increasing density. This is in most cases due to the content of asphaltenes in it, compounds of large hydrocarbons with a high molecular composition. The viscosity of oil increases exponentially with an increase in the amount of asphaltenes contained in it [3-4]. Density and viscosity are key properties in determining the profitability of the development of a heavy oil field. Heavy oil is traditionally sold cheaper than light hydrocarbons, since an energy-intensive quality improvement process must be carried out before using it. On the other hand, high viscosity values lead to low productivity and the need to invest in more expensive methods of increasing oil production.

Around the world, some of the largest deposits in terms of reserves, such as Mexico's Cantarell, are reaching or have already reached a maximum and have begun to experience a decline in production rates. The largest oil fields remained mainly on the territory of the Middle Eastern OPEC countries. At the same time, global oil demand continues to grow every year, which is partly facilitated by the fast-growing economies of China and India. The decline in light oil production, combined with an increase in demand, led to an increase in oil prices and prompted the search for alternative energy sources.

In the future, huge deposits of heavy oil and bitumen, which are located in the Western Hemisphere, are being put into development. These unconventional resources are harder and more expensive to extract, so they were practically not affected in the past. However, between the nearly 500 billion barrels of recoverable Canadian oil sands and the more than 200 billion barrels of recoverable Venezuelan heavy oil, the world may soon have access to oil sources almost equivalent to those in the Middle East.

With the rise in oil prices in 2005 and 2006, investments in these more complex oil fields are rapidly increasing. In fact, the U.S. oil industry alone has invested \$86 billion in "new hydrocarbons" since 2000, developing technologies to extract and process the worst grades of oil, such as heavy oil and bitumen, into a form more suitable for use in refineries, as well as to convert waste and residual hydrocarbons into valuable products. The revealed volumes of heavy oil, superheavy oil and bitumen are estimated at about 4,800 gigabarrels (Ggbl), that is, they correspond to the light oil resources explored so far. Only a few of these heavy raw materials have already been developed, only 1-2%. (Fig. 1.3) [5-6].

Распределение нефтяных запасов

Figure 1.3 - Distribution of oil reserves in the world by groups

About 87% of these resources are represented by oil sands and bitumen in Canada, superheavy oil in Venezuela and heavy oil in Russia (Table 1.1). Orinoco Belt resources in Venezuela are estimated at 1200 Gbl and bitumen in Canada at about 1700 Gbbl. In recent years, there has been more and more information about the countries of the former Soviet Union. According to various sources, Russia apparently has from 600 to 1300 gigabarrels of heavy oil and bitumen resources. Canada is very rich in reserves of heavy oil and bitumen, and, according to OIP estimates, its reserve is 400 billion. m³, which is twice the total reserves of conventional oil in the Middle East [7].

The ratio of the relative mobility of the oil and water phases is expressed in the form of the formula

$$M = (k_w \mu_o) / (k_o \mu_w),$$

where M is the coefficient of mobility, k_w is the coefficient of relative permeability to water in water-saturated zones, k_o is the coefficient of relative permeability to oil in oil-saturated zones, μ_o is the coefficient of viscosity of oil, and μ_w is the coefficient of viscosity of water. A higher mobility coefficient leads to the fact that water, when filtered through areas saturated with oil, leaves behind oil-saturated areas not covered by displacement [8]. However, the mobility coefficient <1 contributes to higher oil recovery with uniform displacement of oil. Consequently, when a polymer is added to the injected water, the viscosity of the water increases, which reduces its mobility and increases the overall effectiveness of the polymer action.

Chemical methods of flooding have a very high displacement efficiency in laboratory studies [9]. The oil displacement coefficient (Ed) reflects the amount of oil remaining in small or dead-end pores after the end

of tertiary production [10]. Taber [8] expressed the ratio of viscous and capillary forces responsible for oil retention and designated it as "capillary number (N_{ca})":

$$N_{ca} = (\mu_w v_w) / (\sigma_{ow}),$$

where μ_w is the viscosity; v_w is the fluid flow velocity; σ_{ow} is the water-oil interfacial tension coefficient. Significant oil recovery occurs when large changes in the number of capillaries occur; estimates show that a 1000-fold change in the number of capillaries is required for significant oil recovery [11]. Surfactants reduce interfacial tension and polymer adsorption on the rock surface, which increases the number of capillaries sufficient to overcome capillary forces, thereby increasing the mobility of oil [12]. Operations with fluids based on alkali, polymers and surfactants (ASP) or surfactants and polymers (SP) have shown equal or greater success in increasing oil recovery than flooding [13].

Of the studied polymers for the Vostochny Moldabek deposit, the Flopaam 5115VHM polymer turned out to be the most suitable for high solubility and viscosity readings. This polymer allows you to obtain the highest viscosity at a concentration of 2000 ppm, which could be a good target value for this parameter.

The required concentration of the active polymer should be determined on the basis of economic calculations.

For the Zaburunye deposit, Flopaam 5205VHM and FLOCOMB 6725 polymers were selected as suitable options. The required concentration of the active polymer will be approximately 1500 ppm, which corresponds to a viscosity of 13 sP for Flopaam 5205VHM and 16.5 sP for FLOCOMB 6725.

FLOCOMB 6725 is a high molecular weight polymer, and the target viscosity value can be achieved at lower concentrations, as can be seen from Figure 1.4.

Figure 1.4 Viscosity of various polymers as a function of concentration in the reservoir waters of the Zaburunye deposit at a temperature of 39 °C

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